

dtw: <https://w3id.org/def/dtw#>
dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
td: <https://www.w3.org/2019/wot/td#>
hctl: <https://www.w3.org/2019/wot/hypermedia#>
dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema>